

FOOTSTEP ENERGY HARVESTER

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Abstract— The Footstep Energy Harvester is a compact and renewable energy-based system that is designed to convert mechanical pressure from human footsteps to electrical energy. This system generates energy from the daily activities of humans instead of depending on the conventional power sources. This work uses a set of piezoelectric discs which are used to generate electrical energy when the discs are compressed. Each piezoelectric disc produces an alternating voltage when it is compressed. This is then rectified and regulated using diodes, capacitor, resistors and transistor. The energy is stored and is displayed through LCD display. As the global energy demands are increasing, the need for renewable, sustainable, scalable and user-friendly solutions are also increasing. The Footstep energy harvester offers many advantages in terms of environmental sustainability, autonomy as well as zero fuel cost. On the other hand, there are limitations such as poor mechanical durability, non-linear piezoelectric response and high installation cost over large area. The results confirms that the system generates energy which can be used for low power applications and is feasible of harvesting energy from the daily activities of humans. With further optimization, this system can be implemented in public places to support sustainable and self-powered infrastructure.

Keywords— Electrical energy, Footstep, Piezoelectric discs, Energy harvesting

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I. INTRODUCTION

The globe is facing serious issues in the demand of energy and power source generation in the recent times. In such a situation the hunt for sustainable and decentralized power sources becomes an utmost priority. One promising approach is the use of footstep energy harvester that converts the human foot mechanical energy to appropriate electrical energy. In contrast to the traditional grid-based power, footstep harvesters operate locally, using piezoelectric, electromagnetic or triboelectric mechanisms to generate power directly from everyday movement[1]. This system, even though is at its beginning stages of evolution has been integrated into floors, pavements, or public walkways, enabling energy capture in high-traffic regions without altering user behaviour. Apart from been known for its high renewability, it has also offered benefits in powering low-energy devices, supporting smart-city applications, and enhancing sustainability in public spaces. However, the technology is still developing and faces challenges such as low power outputs, material durability and cost effectiveness[2]. The work aims to explore the working principles, existing limitations and future potentials of footstep energy harvesting systems. By examining smarter materials, architecture and real-world development this research tries to explain how the human organised micro system created can lent a huge impact on the future development scopes. Furthermore, as urban infrastructures continue to expand integrating harvesters such as transportation hubs, educational institutions and commercial complexes. The work also tries to evaluate emerging optimisation techniques and hybrid energy harvesting approaches. Through this comprehensive study, we aim to demonstrate the vast potential of footstep energy harvesting in shaping a more efficient, flexible and energy efficient world[3].

A. Problem statement

The growing global energy crises and the depletion of conventional power sources have made it essential to explore alternative methods of energy generation and the following are the challenges:

- There is a need for alternative renewable energy sources to reduce dependency on conventional electricity and promote sustainable power generations[4].
- Existing energy harvesting methods are complex, making them unsuitable for small scale, low power public applications.

- There are no inbuilt monitoring systems to show the amount of energy generated and number of footsteps generated instantly[5].
- Human footsteps produce mechanical energy that is usually wasted especially in busy places such as malls, railway stations and so on.
- A compact, affordable and efficient system is required to collect, store and display the energy generated from human footsteps.[6]

Thus, these issues require thoughtful engineering approaches to develop harvesting systems that are not only efficient, but also durable, cheaper and suitable for real world implementation.

B. Proposed Solution

To make footstep energy harvesting practical for everyday life, the proposed solution focuses on improving the energy conversion part through optimised use of piezo electric devices, allowing high power outputs. To withstand continuous foot pressure and extend the system lifespan and make power storing easy and conservative. On a larger scale we can also use modular floors to get optimum results from the existing human motion. Additionally smart control tool, durable materials and real time monitoring could further enhance performance, reliability and maintain efficiency. Such approaches can transform footstep harvester from an experimental scale to a vital, scalable and sustainable power generator method for modern urban environments.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Circuit Diagram

The circuit diagram of the methodology used is given in Figure 1. It uses 12 piezo discs to convert mechanical stress applied on it to electrical energy and this energy generated is given to bridge rectifier followed by a capacitor that acts as a rectifier and filter respectively, as the input generated is in AC, it has to be converted to DC[7].

ARDUINO NANO is the microcontroller take power from the battery pack used to sense the voltage generated from footsteps applied or the pressure applied on the piezo discs and calculates the number of footsteps, energy generated and the battery level. It also controls the LED and transistor outputs. It sends the data to LCD[8].

LCD I2C MODULE + 16x2 DISPLAY is connected to ARDUINO NANO as shown in the above circuit diagram which makes the display easy to interface that shows total footsteps counted, energy generated from piezo output[9].

BATTERY stores the energy and are charged gradually through rectified energy. When a footstep occurs, NPN transistor (BC547) allows LED to blink. The switch allows enabling/disabling the entire system. The transistor is used to control battery charging flow or drive the LED indicator when energy is being harvested.[10]

Fig 1 Circuit diagram of energy harvester

B. *Work flow*

The workflow is described in Figure 2. The pressure applied on the piezo discs to generate a mechanical stress. Piezoelectric Sensor Array Converts the mechanical stress by the footsteps to electrical energy. Bridge Rectifier Converts AC from the output of piezo discs to DC by rectifying it. Capacitor is used as filter to remove the ripples from the rectified output. Battery Charging Section is used to drive the Arduino Nano and the I2C display module and can be charged gradually due to rectified energy. ARDIUNO NANO is equivalent to one step and counts the total steps. It also has the control on outputs and turns the LED on with each footstep It takes (amount of voltage generated). 16x2 LCD Display takes the data from the Arduino Nano and displays the output generated which are the number of footsteps and voltage generated across the piezo discs.

Fig 2 Work flow of energy harvester

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The amount of the voltage generated with the footsteps is given in Figure 3. Initially when we provide the power supply the LCD displays a name “Footstep Energy Harvester” and then shows the initializing message before displaying output. Each piezo disc generates 7.2 mV and we are using totally 15 piezo discs which generates 0.108V and tries to power up the LED which is used at the output. The Arduino nano successfully detects the footsteps and shows it using LCD display as shown in the Figure 3 and the number of footsteps shown above is 56 steps. This generated voltage is displayed in LCD display with the help of programmed Arduino Nano which senses the output across piezo discs. To power this Arduino Nano and LCD display we are using a rechargeable battery. When we calculate the open-circuit voltage spikes they are very short due to the connections of rectifiers, filters and the ADC inputs, the transient energy is lost or clamped and average DC across buffer is slow. The amount of voltage generated also depends on the pressure applied very high pressure can help us develop a good amount of voltage.

Fig 3 Voltage generated based on the footsteps

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The work successfully demonstrates a working prototype of footstep energy harvester with the useful integration of piezoelectric discs, ARDUINO microcontroller and a storage unit. The system performs successful conversion of mechanical to electrical energy, storing it efficiently and displaying the step count and voltage generated through the LCD screen. It is safe, simple and effective for its scale

Although the energy generated is limited due to prototype size and material constraint, the core principles were implemented successfully. The inclusion of monitoring electronics has added on to a user-friendly element that helps how footsteps contribute to energy generation. This project illustrates a perfect example that even with basic components that we can model a sustainable micro energy system.

A Future Enhancements

- High energy outputs: The future improvements focus on creating better outputs by using advanced tools of the already existing mechanisms.
- Smart energy managements: By adding on and advancing in the piezo discs, DC-DC convertors and the storage, we make sure that maximum of energy is consumed and almost little is wasted or lost.
- Enhancing durability and safety: The use of reinforced durable materials, anti-slippery pavements and waterproof floors the system generation can be safe and accurate.
- Human powered smart ecosystems: Future scopes wherein these harvesters can feed into a connected network that lights up the nearby sensors creating self-sustained human micro-ecosystems were everyday movements fuels urban infrastructures.

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